

The Algebra of the Equality on Complex Numbers II

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Abstract

The manuscript establish the properties of $Prod_{map}(a_1, a_2) = (a_1)(a_2)$ homomorphism over a monoid of Complex numbers to explain the relation $0 =_A a_1$ and the transitivity property for $-1 \leq 0 \leq 1$

1 Introduction

Equality between two quantities ($a =_A b$) that are different was established on ref [2]; specifically could be concluded that

$$-a =_A a$$

using abstract equality $=_A$ to define such relation since complex plane is established that

$$-a < a \in \mathfrak{R}$$

the case when $a =_A b$ also can be addressed using the properties of squares showed on ref [1,2].

This means that a new algebraic property has been identified and must be established to understand the algebraic equality on complex plane and its relation with the geometrical translation transformation. This work tackle such properties.

2 The equality $a =_A b$ and the function $Prod_{map}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = a \cdot b$

Suppose that \exists a function $Prod_{map} : C \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ such that

$$Add_{map}(a, b) = a \cdot b$$

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On Argand's product we have:

$$Prod_{map}[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] =$$

$$Prod_{map}(ac - bd, ad + bc) = (ac - bd) \cdot (ad + bc)$$

$$= a^2cd + abc^2 - abd^2 - b^2cd$$

If $a = b$

$$= a^2cd + a^2c^2 - a^2d^2 - a^2cd$$

$$= a^2c^2 - a^2d^2$$

$$= a^2(c^2 - d^2)$$

Lets note next property about squares

$$Side_1 = Side_2 = c = d$$

With $Area_{Square} = c \cdot d$ we could establish

$$0 = c^2 - d^2 < c \cdot d$$

By ref[1,2] we have $A_{QII} = A_{QI}$ since where we establish: $-1 = 1$

By trichotomy we must have:

$$-1 < 0 < 1$$

Hence by last two conditions:

$$A_{QII} \leq 0 \leq A_{QI}$$

By ref[1,2] and transitivity we can establish

$$A_{QII} = 0 = A_{QI}$$

i.e. $-1 = 1 = 0$

Hence

$$c^2 - d^2 = c \cdot d$$

Strictly by ref[2]

$$c^2 - d^2 = c \cdot d$$

Multiplying from both sides by a^2

$$a^2(c^2 - d^2) =_A a^2 \cdot c \cdot d$$

$$=_A a \cdot a \cdot c \cdot d$$

$$=_A Prod_{map}(a, a) \cdot Prod_{map}(c, d)$$

Therefore

$$Prod_{map}[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] =_A Prod_{map}(a, b) \cdot Prod_{map}(c, d) \in \mathfrak{R}$$

and

$$Prod_{map}[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] < Prod_{map}(a, b) \cdot Prod_{map}(c, d) \in \mathfrak{R}$$

Note that to establish equality $c^2 - d^2 < c \cdot d$

We must introduce another square in \mathfrak{R} after define $Prod_{map}(c, d) = c \cdot d$

$$Prod_{map}(a, c) \cdot Prod_{map}(a, d) = Prod_{map}(ac, ad)$$

In particular when $a = b = 0$ we have for

$$Prod_{map}[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] = a^2(c^2 - d^2) < a^2cd = Prod_{map}(a, b) \cdot Prod_{map}(c, d)$$

$$0 < 0 ! \text{ (contradiction)}$$

and by transitivity any factorization of the pairs considered into $Prod_{map}$ function also will be zero.

This will imply that

$$Prod_{map}(a, b) : \mathbf{C} \rightarrow \mathfrak{R} \text{ when } =_A \text{ is used}$$

and for $=$ we will have

$$Prod_{map}[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] \leq Prod_{map}(a, b) \cdot Prod_{map}(c, d)$$

being $0 = 0$ true when the pair $(a, b) = (0, 0)$ is considered on the Argand's product.

3 Homomorphism of Monoids for $Prod_{map}$ function

$$c) Prod_{map}(e_C) = e_{\mathfrak{R}}$$

$$Prod_{map}(1, 0) = (1 \cdot 0) = 0 = e_{\mathfrak{R}sum}$$

being last the additive identity in \mathfrak{R} keeping any relationship with usual multiplicative operation defined for real numbers.

4 Congruence Relation $=_A$ and $Prod_{map}$

Def. Any homomorphism $f : X \rightarrow Y$ defines a relation \sim on X by $a \sim b$ if and only if $f(a) = f(b)$. The relation \sim is called the kernel of f . It is a compatible relation on X .

Def. A relation R on a given algebraic structure is called compatible if for each n and each n -ary operation μ defined on the structure: whenever $a_1 R a'_1$ and ... and $a_n R a'_n$, then $\mu(a_1, \dots, a_n) R \mu(a'_1, \dots, a'_n)$.

Proof. a) \supset

With $n = 2$ and $R := <$ and

$$a_1 < a_1$$

$$a_2 < a_2 \dots (a)$$

By trichotomy $a_1 \leq a_1$ or $a_1 > a_1$; on monoid equality of all pairs will be discarded therefore

$$a_1 R a_1 ; a_2 R a_2$$

Hence we obtain $(a_1, a_1), (a_2, a_2)$ by by the other hand Cartesian product property defines next property for such relation:

$$R = \{(a_1, a_1) : (a_1, a_1) \in A_1 \times A_2 \wedge R(a_1, a_1) = True\}$$

If we apply $Prod_{map}$ function we obtain

$$Prod_{map}(a_1, a_2) = a_1 \cdot a_2 < a_1 \cdot a_2 = Prod_{map}(a_1, a_2)$$

If

$$a_1 \cdot a_2 = \alpha^2(c^2 - d^2)$$

and

$$a_1 \cdot a_2 = \alpha^2 \cdot c \cdot d$$

by

Area Square Quadrant *I* = Area Square Quadrant *II*

and with $\alpha = \beta$

$$Prod_{map}(a_1, a_2) =$$

$$Prod_{map}[(\alpha c - \beta d, \alpha d + \beta c)] = Prod_{map}[(\alpha, \beta) \cdot (c, d)]$$

$$= {}_A Prod_{map}(\alpha, \beta) \cdot Prod_{map}(c, d) = (\alpha \cdot \beta) \cdot (c \cdot d)$$

$$= \alpha \cdot \beta \cdot c \cdot d = Prod_{map}(a_1, a_2)$$

Therefore

$$Prod_{map}(a_1, a_2) = {}_A Prod_{map}(a_1, a_2) \in \mathfrak{R}$$

b) \subset

Let be

$$Prod_{map}(a_1, a_2) = {}_A Prod_{map}(a_1, a_2)$$

Hence

$$Prod_{map}(a_1, a_2) < Prod_{map}(a_1, a_2)$$

Developing

$$a_1 \cdot a_2 < a_1 \cdot a_2$$

If

$$a_1 < a_1$$

and

$$a_2 < a_2$$

Henceforth

$Prod_{map}$ homomorphism defines a relation $=_A$ on \mathfrak{R} through the relation $<$

5 References

- [1] Alejandro, J.R. (2004). A Real Approximation to Riemann Hypothesis. J. Math Techniques Comput Math, 3(2), 01-12.
- [2] The Algebra of the Equality on Complex Numbers; M. Díaz; J. R. A.; (scribd 2024)